

Pernicious ignorance and the marginalisation of Third Space professionals

Reflections on lived experience

Dustin Hosseini

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The discussions for this session had this article as a starting point:

Hosseini, D. D. (2025). Pernicious ignorance and the marginalisation of third space professionals: reflections on lived experience. *Journal of Learning Development in Higher Education, Special edition* (33). <https://doi.org/10.47408/jldhe.vi33.1234>

The paper surfaces a recurring challenge encompassing the recognition and visibility of third space professionals in higher education as educators who experience silencing stemming from pernicious ignorance. Accordingly, Dustin uses Dotson's notion of pernicious ignorance (2011, p. 238) to analyse a reflective vignette to illustrate a challenge that undermines third space practitioners.

His aim is to equip readers with theory that they can use to counter negative workplace behaviours, whether observed, experienced or both, while strengthening their positions as third space professionals.

Reference

Dotson, K. (2011). Tracking epistemic violence, tracking practices of silencing. *Hypatia*, 2, 236–257. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1527-2001.2011.01177.x>

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